

Emigration to South Africa: A Recent Hub for Opportunities to Indian Youth

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Introduction

The advent of Europeans to the land of Africa changed. Its political Social and Economic structure vehemently. After the Boer War the Dutch her sway over South Africa completely fell into the hands of the English. South Africa was a centre of attracts of Indian workers especially in the region of Cape Town, Pretoria and Johannesburg. When the British imperialism ended forever the age old system apartheid also ended forever. The new South African government under the leadership of Nelson Mandela widely opens her gates to Indian Youth. This enunciated the Indian youths to seek their fortune there especially in the field of Agro-processing, IT, Textile, Automotives, etc.

South Africa, a sovereign state, and South Africa reserves the right to determine who is allowed entry is allowed into the country, and under what conditions. Therefore, the new white paper on international Migration affirms South Africa's sovereign right to determine the entry and residence conditions for foreign nationals in line with its national interest. Young men have constituted a significant proportion of those migrating annually, but women and children are also in large numbers. The overall number of migrants has been increasing day-by-day owing to opportunities offered by rapid transport, accessibility to communications as well as "push" and "pull" factors. "Pull" factors include economic and professional opportunities and safety. "push" factors include economic inequality, conflicts persecution, degraded environments, and climate change. In general, South Africans are proud of the role they are playing internationally to strengthen collective peace and security and confront problems such as climate change, pandemics, and poverty.

Objectives

1. To explore the potential opportunities prevailing in South Africa.
2. To identify the different arena of job opportunities in South Africa.
3. To conscientize the emerging youth in India

Methodology

To understand the methodology used to complete this paper, to justify and authenticating the research procedure employed to meet the set objectives and answers.

This study is based only secondary data that includes articles from news papers, Journals, Websites and various reports published the government of South Africa and certain other organisations.

Data Analysis

South Africa is primarily a parliamentary representative democratic republic. Nelson Mandela was the first president who was elected in accordance with new constitution of South Africa. The incumbent is Cyril Ramaphosa, who was selected by the National Assembly on 15 February 2018 following the resignation of Jacob Zuma.

Business visa may be issued by the Department of Home Affairs to a foreigner intending to establish an investment in South Africa by which he or she may be employed. The Act calls for the investment of R 5 million for business and make sure that he/she may employ at least sixty percentages of South African citizens or permanent residents to get both temporary and permanent business visa.

Majority of business concerns do not number of capital investment as large as R 5 million and in certain cases, the investor is allowed to reduce this amount and can opt for smaller investment if one's business falls within the certain categories.

The industries are

Agro-processing

This industry is enveloping several small-scale businesses such as Fisheries and aquaculture, Food-Processing, Beverages, High-value organic foods, Biofuels, oils, and Diversification of biomass etc.

Business Process Outsourcing and IT Enabled Services

These newly born industries provide Call centres, Back office Processing, KPO, Shared corporate services, Enterprise solutions, And Legal Out sourcing capital.

Capital, Transport Equipment, Metals, and Electrical Machinery and Apparatus

In this category includes various capital intensive business units which are providing better opportunities in South Africa for young Indian entrepreneurs. E.g. Basic Iron And steel, Metal work service category, Electricity distribution and apparatus. etc.

Electro and Technical

Electro and technical area is providing opportunities for young Indians in South Africa Especially for software engineers and technically skilled professionals and entrepreneurs. e.g., financial software

Textile, Clothing, and Leather

Textile and leather industry in South Africa requires highly talented young Indian people to Participate in this sector which provides massive employment opportunities for youngsters and better opportunities for young entrepreneurs.

Pulp, Paper, and Furniture

It is one of most profitable sectors which are providing better opportunities for young Indians. In India, we have lot Institutions for the development of this skill. E.g. Publishing, Printing, Furniture etc.

Automotive and Components

This segment includes Automotives and their allied sectors which provide high employability in the world. These Opportunities are established by South Africa. Young Indians can easily acquire through their engineering and entrepreneurial skill. The engineering Institution Seek the “Global Engineers”. E.g. Air conditioners, components, engines, instrument parts, etc.

Low-cost Private schools

Rapid population Growth, lack of funding, corruption and neglect have caused deterioration on the quality of education in South Africa. But the government of South Africa estimates that 25 percentage of African students-a total of 66 million-will be enrolled in private schools by the year 2021. Hence the assure Young Indian teachers and educators will get massive opportunities in this segment

Healthcare Services

Health care is the most promising service sector in South Africa. In India large number of highly talented young healthcare professionals is available. So that Indian youths can accrue this opportunity in South Africa through better orientations among our professionals. Now days, large numbers of Africans are seeking medical help outside the Africa. According to the IFC, Africa’s healthcare market could be doubled in size just ten years

Logistics Management

Last but not least, rising urbanization needs more opportunities in the logistics sector. The future of Africa is in cities. By 2030, half of the continents 1.4 billion people will be located by cities. Currently, about 60 African cities have a population of over 1 million people. In this juncture, Indian youth can easily tap the opportunity through their skills in the logistics management. Most of the Indian business schools and Management studies provide this skill through their Institutions.

Summary

Africa is a continent that significantly rewards problem-solvers, and plays a pivotal role in ensuring financial stability. South Africa is going through very exciting stage at the moment and there is lots of opportunity to be involved in this emerging economy and the government welcomes everyone wishing to invest and create employment. The markets are highly lucrative especially for small business owners, and the government welcomes anyone who wants to invest. South Africa is often called “world in one country”. Good governance, which includes the rule of law and initiatives to reduce corruption, builds trust amongst the population outside investors. Sound economic policies that promote growth contribute to creating jobs that can be filled by those reaching working age.

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